

Project Title	Blue-Cloud 2026: A federated European FAIR and Open Research Ecosystem for oceans, seas, coastal and inland waters
Project Acronym	Blue-Cloud 2026
Project Number	101094227
Type of project	RIA – Research and Innovation Action
Topics	HORIZON-INFRA-2022-EOSC-01
Starting date of Project	01 January 2023
Duration of the project	42 months
Website	www.blue-cloud.org

D2.5 – Established BDI sub-setting APIs and Data Lakes – Documentation Report

Work Package	WP2 FAIR compliant Discovery and Access services for marine domains & beyond
Task	T2.3 Vertical expansion: developing and deploying sub-setting services at BDIs and Blue-Cloud Data Lakes
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Version	V0.1
Due Date	28/02/2025
Submission Date	04/03/2025

Dissemination Level

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	PU: Public
<input type="checkbox"/>	CO: Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission)
<input type="checkbox"/>	EU-RES. Classified Information: RESTREINT UE (Commission Decision 2005/444/EC)
<input type="checkbox"/>	EU-CON. Classified Information: CONFIDENTIEL UE (Commission Decision 2005/444/EC)
<input type="checkbox"/>	EU-SEC. Classified Information: SECRET UE (Commission Decision 2005/444/EC)

Version History

Revision	Date	Editors	Comments
0.1	12/12/2024	Dick M.A. Schaap (MARIS) and contributors	Table of Content
0.2	19/12/2024	Dick M.A. Schaap (MARIS) and contributors	Inputs in Section 1
0.3	12/01/2025	Dick M.A. Schaap (MARIS) and contributors	Inputs in Section 2
0.4	29/01/2025	Dick M.A. Schaap (MARIS) and contributors	Inputs in Section 3
0.5	04/02/2025	Dick M.A. Schaap (MARIS) and contributors	Inputs in Section 4
0.6	12/02/2025	Dick M.A. Schaap (MARIS) and contributors	Further refinements of Sections 1 and 2
0.7	19/02/2025	Dick M.A. Schaap (MARIS) and contributors	Further refinements of Sections 3 and 4
0.8	03/03/2025	Dick M.A. Schaap (MARIS) and contributors	Executive Summary
0.9	04/03/2025	Pasquale Pagano (CNR), Rita Giuffrida (Trust-IT)	Quality check
1.0	04/03/2025	Pasquale Pagano (CNR)	Final version for submission

Keywords

Blue-Cloud 2026, EOSC, Marine research, Open Science; Data Discovery; Data Federation; Data Access; Subsetting, Data Lakes, Federated Access

Disclaimer

The Blue-Cloud 2026 project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101094227. Views and opinions expressed are those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Commission. Neither the European Union nor the European Commission can be held responsible for them.

Glossary of terms

Item	Description
API	Application Programming Interface
BDI	Blue Data Infrastructure
BEACON	Data Lake solution
CDI	Common Data Index (SeaDataNet)
CMEMS	Copernicus Marine Environment Monitoring Service
CMC INSTAC	Copernicus Marine In Situ Assembly Centre
CSW	Catalogue Service for the Web (OGC standard)
DAB	Discovery and Access Broker
DD&AS	Data Discovery & Access Service
DTO	Digital Twins of the Oceans
EDITO	European Digital Twin of the Oceans infrastructure
EMODnet	European Marine Observation and Data network
EMSO	European Multidisciplinary Seafloor and water column Observatory
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ERDDAP	Environmental Research Division's Data Access Program
EuroGOOS	European contribution to GOOS program
GUI	Graphical User Interface

Item	Description
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
NODC	National Oceanographic Data Centre
NVS	NERC Vocabulary Server
OAI-PMH	Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting
OGC	Open Geospatial Consortium
SeaDataNet	pan-European network for marine and ocean data management
SQL	Structured Query Language
TSC	Technical and Scientific Committee
UI	User Interface
VLab	Virtual Laboratory
VRE	Virtual Research Environment
WFS	Web Feature Service (OGC standard)
WMS	Web Map Service (OGC standard)
WMTS	Web Map Tile Service (OGC standard)
WOD	World Ocean Database
XML	Extensible Markup Language
ZARR	Effective format to store large N-dimensional data in the cloud and access chunks

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

A one-year-long consultation and prototyping phase has resulted in concrete plans for establishing data subsetting capabilities in the Blue-Cloud ecosystem and implementing that vision by deploying a series of data lakes at the Blue-Cloud VRE for data repositories and data collections in support of VRE users and developers of the WorkBenches. After consideration and positive tests on selected BDI data collections, it was decided at the latest Blue-Cloud Scientific and Technical Committee (STC) meeting, 5-6 March 2024, in Amsterdam - The Netherlands, to embrace the **Beacon** technology, as developed by MARIS, for deploying data lakes at the Blue-Cloud VRE for arranging data provision for WorkBenches 1 and 2 and also for VLabs.

The analysis and decisions about the way forward have been documented in Deliverable **D2.4 -BDI sub-setting APIs and Data Lakes – Concept and Specifications Report** - which was released in early May 2024. It gives details about the envisioned data lake configurations and also about the Beacon technology that is being adopted for powering the data lakes. Furthermore, it describes the implementation planning and related actions.

As a follow-up, developments have been undertaken for configuring the Beacon software and deployments have been established of Beacon instances, prioritised by the data requirements of WorkBenches 1 (T&S) and 2 (eutrophication). In total 8 so-called monolithic Beacon instances have been deployed for different data collections and BDIs. The term ‘monolithic’ is used to indicate that the Beacon instance concerns one data collection or BDI. After initial configuration at a MARIS server, all 8 instances have been deployed operationally at the Blue-Cloud Virtual Research Environment (VRE). All have been integrated with the **D4Science federated AAI service**, by which access is arranged. All Beacon instances also have been provided with a Jupyter-notebook which sits on the Beacon API and which makes it easier for the users to interact. The notebooks already contain several queries and users can adapt their own notebooks. There is a Beacon website¹ available for more information including detailed documentation² for end-users on how to work with Beacon.

After considerable testing and feedback rounds on monolithic Beacon instances by members of the WorkBench teams, as a next step, two integrated Beacon instances have been initiated. These are merging data set collections from several monolithic Beacon instances. The challenge is to deliver harmonised collections, federated from the monolithic instances with different data models. For that purpose, a core metadata – data profile has been formulated by the WorkBench 1 and 2 teams which is populated by

¹ <https://beacon.maris.nl/>

² <https://maris-development.github.io/beacon/>

extracting and mapping from the monolithic instances. This applies not only to syntax but also to semantics. Harmonisation is not applied only for parameters and units, but also for a core set of metadata, that have been selected by the WorkBench teams as necessary for harmonisation and their following actions. For the merging use is made of the federation capabilities of the Beacon technology, while for the semantic mapping, use is made of the Semantic Analyser system of NOC-BODC. Any necessary unit conversion rules can be retrieved and applied using factors and offsets as listed.

The considerable progress made is documented in this deliverable ***D2.5 - Established BDI sub-setting APIs and Data Lakes – Documentation Report***. It gives information about the Beacon technology and the activities undertaken towards the deployment of the 8 monolithic and 2 merged Beacon instances. It also gives an outlook towards the next steps on how the merged Beacon instances will be used by the WorkBench teams as part of their analytical pipelines. Further activities are required around Beacon to achieve full operational and robust data provision workflows on which the WorkBench teams can build their targeted analyses for generating high-quality EOVS collections. These activities are specified in this Deliverable and will be finalised in the third project year.

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1. Introduction

The DD&AS supports discovery and download of **predefined data objects**, which are documented with metadata records. A user then might retrieve tens of thousands of individual data sets that he/she has to process to retrieve the specific data that he/she is after. Therefore, in addition to the DD&AS service, developments have been initiated in the Blue-Cloud 2026 project for exploring and establishing **sub-setting or slicing functionality** on major repositories, such as the Blue-Cloud BDIs, but also on international repositories such as the World Ocean Database (WOD), which are relevant with complementary data sets. Sub-setting aims to work at the level of the data sets, and facilitate extracting specific parameters and values from the data sets, for instance all temperature observations with temperature value > 10 degrees in October 2020 between 50 and 100 metres in depth. Deploying sub-setting functionality on major repositories allows to build and maintain **data lakes** for specific parameters by regular extractions.

The search for establishing sub-setting functionality started at the first Scientific and Technical Committee (STC) meeting, 28-29 March 2023 in Amsterdam – Netherlands, where a brainstorm was held on data lakes, and different technical solutions. At this meeting, a prototype was demonstrated of **Beacon**, a new technology developed by MARIS. The STC group indicated great interest in further exploring and deploying this technology from the perspective of BDIs and Work Benches, as it promised to make it possible to slice through data files as managed by BDIs, querying for parameters, depth, location, time period, and possible other criteria, and to generate homogeneous result files which contain the selected values and associated metadata. A prerequisite for the subsetting is that it really should perform on millions of data sets as it would then allow a user to browse through the resulting data, for instance in a viewer using sliders for depth, parameters, and dates at a comfortable pace without having to wait.

A one-year long consultation and prototyping phase has resulted in concrete plans for establishing data subsetting capabilities in the Blue-Cloud ecosystem and implementing that vision by deploying a series of data lakes at the Blue-Cloud Virtual Research Environment (VRE) for data repositories and data collections in support of VRE users and developers of the WorkBenches. After consideration and positive tests on a number of BDI data collections, it was decided at the latest STC meeting, 5-6 March 2024, in Amsterdam - The Netherlands, to embrace the **Beacon** technology for deploying data lakes for Blue-Cloud 2026 at the VRE, arranging data provision for WorkBenches 1 and 2.

The analysis and decisions about the way forward have been documented in Deliverable **D2.4 -BDI sub-setting APIs and Data Lakes – Concept and Specifications Report** - which was released early May 2024. It details the envisioned data lake configurations and also about the Beacon technology that is being

adopted for powering the data lakes. Furthermore, it describes the implementation planning and related actions.

The specifications and vision from D2.4 have been given a follow-up in the following months. The related activities and achieved results will be described in this new Deliverable ***D2.5 - Established BDI sub-setting APIs and Data Lakes – Documentation Report*** -. Moreover, it will document the next steps planned to achieve full operational and robust data provision workflows on which the WorkBench teams can build their targeted analyses for generating high-quality EOVS collections.

2. BEACON - high-performance big data subsetting technology

2.1. Description of Beacon

Beacon is a high performance data lake designed for subsetting and storing large quantities of climate data. Beacon is written by MARIS from scratch in Rust and C and makes use of many new OS kernel APIs to enable its high performance. The goal of a Beacon data lake is to provide an easy-to-use, fast, reliable, and scalable solution for storing, processing, and querying large amounts of climate and marine environmental data.

Features of Beacon are:

- **Direct and Powerful Subsetting:** Beacon facilitates on-the-fly subsetting of millions of datasets and responds within milliseconds. It enables subsetting using the following methods:
 - Range (min, max) filtering of every column/parameter
 - Polygon filtering
 - Filtering on metadata
- **Ease of Use:** The data lake provides a simple and intuitive REST API with swagger documentation, making it easy to store, process, and retrieve/query your data.
- **Cross Platform:** Support for the following platforms:
 - Docker
 - Linux
 - Windows
- **Understands Every Data Dimensionality:** Beacon understands how dimensionality in data sets represents the data and thus doesn't require to harmonise or prepare datasets. Whether the dataset is 1-dimensional or 4-dimensional, Beacon understands it.
- **Data Harmonisation:** With Beacon, users are able to harmonise various parts of their datasets and build even more powerful products. Various parameters can be harmonised together or even converted between different units, all on the fly using Beacon. This can all be done within a Query.
- **Many Output Formats:** Beacon can create a single harmonised output in many different formats such as:
 - NetCDF

- Parquet
- JSON
- GeoJSON
- CSV
- Arrow IPC
- WebODV

ASCII

- **Performance:** Beacon is designed with performance in mind. Subsetting from millions of observational data records within seconds can enable a new range of applications to be built.
- **Scalability:** The Beacon data lake is designed to be highly scalable, allowing to store and process terabytes of data without sacrificing performance.
- **Union Queries:** With Beacon, it is possible to run union queries which enables users to run multiple individual queries at once and combine the results of those individual queries into a single aggregated and harmonised result file.
- **Federated Queries:** Using federated queries, it is possible to run a query against another Beacon instance instead of just the one you're running the query against. In combination with union queries, this would allow users to run multiple federated queries against various Beacon instances and produce a single harmonised output file to the user.
- **Dynamic Chunking:** Beacon is able to create chunks of loaded datasets which will allow for even more efficient querying. Beacon makes use of a method called, Relative Optimised Chunking, that chunks datasets based on their actual data contents, instead of the dimensions provided by the dataset. This means observations of a dataset will be chunked into parts that are in close proximity to each other (Eg. in longitude, latitude, time and depth). This allows for more efficient data retrieval, as Beacon can just load in the chunks required instead of the entire data array for a variable (e.g. temperature).

Beacon website: <https://beacon.maris.nl>

Detailed documentation: <https://maris-development.github.io/beacon/>

2.2. Beacon Binary Format

The Beacon Binary Format is designed to deliver high-performance data access and small data size. This format provides efficient storage and retrieval of data using variables and dimensions, accompanied by attributes to store metadata. The Beacon Binary Format draws inspiration from existing formats like NetCDF but introduces improvements to achieve significantly faster performance and support for multiple readers simultaneously.

Many existing formats involve deserialization costs, which can be a performance bottleneck when dealing with large datasets. Additionally, compression techniques employed in some formats can introduce overhead and hinder data access speed. The Beacon Binary Format addresses these issues by eliminating deserialization costs and using performance focused compression algorithms while ensuring efficient data representation.

The Beacon Binary Format offers several key features that distinguish it from other formats and make it a desirable choice for high-performance data processing:

- Zero Copy Deserialization Cost:** The Beacon Binary Format eliminates the need for deserialization, allowing for direct access to data without incurring performance penalties. This advantage is achieved by storing data in a format that is directly compatible with the target language, avoiding the need for conversion or parsing operations during data retrieval. This format is designed to optimise data retrieval, resulting in improved performance, especially for large-scale datasets.
- Small Data Size:** The Beacon Binary Format focuses on minimising data size through compression without losing any performance. By utilising a compact binary representation, it achieves reduced storage requirements, facilitating faster data transfer and reducing storage costs.
- Variables and Dimensions:** The format adopts a flexible structure by employing variables and dimensions to organise and represent data. Variables allow for the storage of multi-dimensional arrays, while dimensions define the size and shape of these arrays. This structure offers versatility and facilitates the storage of complex data structures.
- Metadata Storage using Attributes:** Metadata plays a crucial role in describing and providing additional context to the stored data. Beacon employs attributes to store metadata, enabling the association of descriptive information, annotations, and other relevant attributes with the variables or on a global level with the dataset. This feature enhances data interpretability and facilitates efficient data management.

- **Simultaneous Multiple Readers:** The Beacon Binary Format supports concurrent access by multiple readers. This capability allows for parallel processing and efficient distribution of computational tasks across multiple threads or systems, contributing to improved performance in scenarios involving high-volume data access.

NetCDF, a popular data format for scientific and geospatial data, shares similarities with the Beacon Binary Format. However, the Beacon Binary Format improves upon NetCDF in several ways:

- **Enhanced Performance:** By eliminating deserialization costs and using performance focused compression algorithms, the Beacon Binary Format achieves higher performance compared to NetCDF. These optimizations reduce data access latency and enable faster computation on the stored data.
- **Concurrent Readers:** Unlike NetCDF, which typically supports a single reader at a time, Beacon Binary Format allows for concurrent access by multiple readers. This feature is particularly advantageous in scenarios where parallel processing and distributed computing are crucial.
- **Arrow Arrays:** Beacon Binary Format uses the “Arrow” memory layout for storing multi-dimensional arrays. This is key due to many of the high-performance tools utilizing “arrow arrays” as their input to start computational operations (eg. Polars, DuckDB, DataFusion). By storing the arrays as “arrow arrays”, it allows other high-performance tools to directly use it as input without having to translate the internal memory layout, allowing us to build data pipelines without translation layers making it true “zero-cost”.

2.3. Beacon Performance Indications

Beacon offers powerful query capabilities and can filter on ranges, polygons and metadata. To illustrate this a test was done by loading Beacon with an increasing number of NetCDF files for Temperature and Salinity as derived from the SeaDataNet CDI Data Discovery and Access service.

In total more than 2.5 Million NetCDF files were loaded into Beacon after which queries were performed. For this test an instance of Beacon was deployed on a relatively small server (8 cores and 32 GB RAM). This implies that even a modern laptop will give even better results, not to speak of fast computer clusters as available in the Blue-Cloud VRE (D4Science e-infrastructure). The following image gives the results of the test queries, which are very good and can be repeated with different queries without any extra effort.

PERFORMANCE

Figure 1- Performance of Beacon queries for case with increasing number of SeaDataNet NetCDF files loaded into Beacon instance

3. Beacon deployments for BDI data collections

As a result of the discussions between WP2 and WP3 WorkBench teams and the overall discussions at the STC meetings, two main use cases have been formulated.

- A number of Beacon instances, each for selected data from a specific BDI, and made available for all Blue-Cloud VRE users;
- Two Beacon instances for WorkBench 1 respectively WorkBench 2, merging and harmonising selected data from multiple BDIs, and with regular and controlled updating mechanism.

3.1. Monolithic Beacon instances configured for selected BDIs and data collections

Beacon deployments

Together with the WorkBench 1 and 2 teams a shortlist has been made of BDI data collections that are relevant as input for the generation of EOVS for Temperature & Salinity (T&S) (WorkBench 1) and Eutrophication (WorkBench 2). Developments have been undertaken by MARIS for configuring the Beacon software and deployments have been established of Beacon instances, first at the MARIS servers. Later, after thorough testing in particular by members of the WorkBench 1 and 2 teams, these monolithic Beacon instances have also been deployed at the Blue-Cloud VRE. The term ‘monolithic’ is used to indicate that the Beacon instance concerns one data collection or BDI.

BDI data collection	Beacon instance	WorkBench
CORA Profile data, retrieved from Copernicus Marine Service: INSITU_GLO_PHY_TS_DISCRETE_MY_013_001	beacon-cora-pr.maris.nl beacon-cora-pr.d4science.org	WB1
CORA Timeseries data, retrieved from Copernicus Marine Service: INSITU_GLO_PHY_TS_DISCRETE_MY_013_001	beacon-cora-ts.maris.nl beacon-cora-ts.d4science.org	WB1
Euro-Argo data, retrieved from S3 bucket	beacon-argo.maris.nl beacon-argo.d4science.org	WB1
SeaDataNet T&S data collection, retrieved from EGI-ACE webODV (1950-2019)	beacon-cdi-ts.maris.nl beacon-seadatanet-ts.d4science.org	WB1
SeaDataNet CDI T&S Incremental data, retrieved from SeaDataNet (2019-2024)	beacon-cdi-incremental.maris.nl	WB1

World Ocean Database (WOD) actual depths, retrieved from ncei.noaa.gov	beacon-wod.maris.nl beacon-wod.d4science.org	WB1 + WB2
EMODnet Chemistry North East Atlantic Collection (subset of the complete collection) retrieved from EMODnet Chemistry WebODV (Eutrophication_Atlantic_profiles_2023_unrestricted.odv)	beacon-emod-chem.maris.nl beacon-emodnet-chemistry.d4science.org	WB2
BGC data, retrieved from Copernicus Marine Service: INSITU_GLO_BGC_DISCRETE_MY_013_046	beacon-cmems.maris.nl beacon-bgc.d4science.org	WB2

Table 1- Overview of deployed monolithic Beacon instances

Remarks: Initially, it was planned by WorkBench 1 to work with the existing SeaDataNet T&S data collection product which has been generated in the EU SeaDataCloud project (2016-2021) and to complement that with recent T&S data from the SeaDataNet CDI service. However, recently it has been decided to work with the full T&S data to be retrieved from the SeaDataNet CDI service. This implies that the WB1 team will have to redo the validation and aggregation of all T&S data sets, but for practical reasons this approach is preferred. For that reason, a new full SeaDataNet T&S CDI data collection beacon instance is being configured, both at MARIS server and at Blue-Cloud VRE, which will replace the function of the two existing SeaDataNet T&S beacon instances.

World Ocean Database as an example of beacon deployments

The World Ocean Database (WOD) is a comprehensive collection of oceanographic data developed and maintained by the National Oceanographic Data Center (NODC) and the World Data Service for Oceanography. It provides a globally integrated and consistent dataset of oceanographic parameters, including temperature, salinity, oxygen, nutrients, and plankton data, among many others. The data is collected from a variety of sources, such as research vessels, autonomous floats, and fixed ocean stations, covering the world's oceans from the surface to the deep sea.

The Beacon node is built on the **World Ocean Database**, available in various formats, including NetCDF, CSV, and ODV-ASCII, hosted at:

<https://www.ncei.noaa.gov/products/world-ocean-database>

Like all deployed Beacon instances, the Beacon WOD node is made accessible via a Jupyter Notebook, which is showcased and explained in more detail below. Such demonstration Notebooks are available on the **Beacon-Blue-Cloud GitHub**:

<https://github.com/maris-development/beacon-blue-cloud/tree/main/notebook-examples>

In order to request data from the WOD Beacon endpoint, the query body needs to be constructed. In the image below you can find an example of how such a query can look. In this case we are querying temperature (parameter), its units, time, depth, longitude and latitude, while filtering on time, depth and location.

```
def query(parameter, mindate, maxdate, minlon, maxlon, minlat, maxlat, mindepth, maxdepth):
    body = {
        "query_parameters": [
            {
                "column_name": parameter,
                "alias": parameter,
                "skip_fill_values": True
            },
            {
                "column_name": f"{parameter}.units",
                "alias": "Unit"
            },
            {
                "column_name": "cf_datetime",
                "alias": "datetime"
            },
            {
                "column_name": "z",
                "alias": "DEPTH"
            },
            {
                "column_name": "lon",
                "alias": "LONGITUDE"
            },
            {
                "column_name": "lat",
                "alias": "LATITUDE"
            },
            {
                "column_name": "dataset",
                "alias": "DATASET",
                "optional": True
            }
        ]
    }
```

```

    },
    {
      "column_name": "WOD_cruise_identif",
      "alias": "cruise-identif",
      "optional": True
    },
    {
      "column_name": "wod_unique_cast",
      "alias": "cast",
      "optional": True
    },
    {
      "column_name": "WMO_ID",
      "alias": "WMO_ID",
      "optional": True
    },
    {
      "column_name": "country",
      "alias": "country",
      "optional": True
    }
  ],
  "filters": [
    {
      "for_query_parameter": "datetime",
      "min": f"{mindate}T00:00:00",
      "max": f"{maxdate}T00:00:00",
      "cast": "timestamp"
    }
  ],
  {
    "for_query_parameter": "DEPTH",
    "min": mindepth,
    "max": maxdepth
  },
  {
    "for_query_parameter": "LONGITUDE",
    "min": minlon,
    "max": maxlon
  },
  {
    "for_query_parameter": "LATITUDE",
    "min": minlat,
    "max": maxlat
  }
],
"output": {
  "format": "ipc"
}
}
return body

query_body = query(parameter, mindate, maxdate, minlon,
                  maxlon, minlat, maxlat, mindepth, maxdepth)

```

Figure 2 - WOD Beacon Jupyter Notebook query

A user can then send this query body to the WOD Beacon endpoint, as seen in the image below. This provides us with the requested data in a dataframe containing all the data fitting the provided filters above. Extra metadata columns can be added to the dataframe by extending the query body above with extra elements.

```
response = requests.post("https://beacon-wod.maris.nl/api/query", json.dumps(query_body), headers={
    "Authorization": f"Bearer {Token}",
    "Content-type": "application/json"
})
```

datetime	Temperature	Unit	DEPTH	LONGITUDE	LATITUDE	DATASET	cruise-identifier	cast	WMO_ID	country	dataset_id
2010-01-01	24.700001	degree_C	1.0	-95.000000	-5.000000	moored buoy	US015955	12327900	2.115095e+09	UNITED STATES	11382402
2010-01-01	26.120001	degree_C	5.0	-110.000000	0.000000	moored buoy	US015969	15272646	2.115095e+09	UNITED STATES	11382406
2010-01-01	26.110001	degree_C	10.0	-110.000000	0.000000	moored buoy	US015969	15272646	2.115095e+09	UNITED STATES	11382406
2010-01-01	28.959999	degree_C	1.5	147.039993	4.960000	moored buoy	JP020811	12327885	2.115114e+09	JAPAN	11382401
2010-01-01	25.440001	degree_C	1.0	-37.880001	20.040001	moored buoy	US026451	12327924	2.115104e+09	UNITED STATES	11382426
...
2010-03-01	29.379999	degree_C	1.0	-34.639999	-18.860001	moored buoy	BR001204	12332326	2.115093e+09	BRAZIL	11390007
2010-03-01	27.370001	degree_C	1.0	-155.009995	7.980000	moored buoy	US015934	12332305	2.115114e+09	UNITED STATES	11389980
2010-03-01	29.860001	degree_C	1.0	-170.020004	-2.170000	moored buoy	US015927	12332281	2.115114e+09	UNITED STATES	11389956
2010-03-01	29.540001	degree_C	1.0	89.989998	-1.670000	moored buoy	JP032626	12327389	2.115115e+09	JAPAN	11389989
2010-03-01	28.430000	degree_C	1.0	165.130005	8.050000	moored buoy	US015890	12332307	2.115114e+09	UNITED STATES	11389966

308863 rows x 11 columns

Figure 3 - WOD Beacon Jupyter notebook query result

In this example we can then very quickly plot this subset of the temperature data between 0-10 meters depth from the WOD collection of the first months of 2010 produced.

Figure 4 - WOD Beacon Jupyter notebook query result plot

Monitoring use of Beacon instances

All Beacon instances have been integrated with the **D4Science federated AAI service**, by which access is arranged. Also, it contributes to maintaining an administration or aggregated log by a service at MARIS to gather KPIs on usage of the Beacon instances. This has been implemented by registering queries, numbers of transactions and data output, divided over original data providers, and identities of users at organisation and country level derived from the federated AAI. The KPIs can be shared through the service at MARIS with managers of BDIs for their specific data sets, so that they are informed about use of their data sets and have justification for their management.

The screenshot shows the 'Beacon' dashboard with a search bar and filters. The 'Executed Queries' section is active, displaying details for query ID 19428. The user 'algemeen' is associated with the query. The query parameters are listed in a JSON format:

```

{
  "query_parameters": [
    {
      "column_name": "COMMON_TEMPERATURE",
      "alias": "COMMON_TEMPERATURE",
      "skip_fill_values": true,
      "optional": true
    },
    {
      "column_name": "COMMON_TEMPERATURE_UNITS",
      "alias": "Unit",
      "skip_fill_values": false,
      "optional": true
    },
    {
      "column_name": "COMMON_TIME",
      "alias": "datetime",
      "skip_fill_values": false,
      "optional": false
    },
    {
      "column_name": "COMMON_TEMPERATURE_QC",
      "alias": "COMMON_TEMPERATURE_qc",
      "skip_fill_values": false,
      "optional": true
    },
    {
      "column_name": "COMMON_TEMPERATURE_P01",
      "alias": "COMMON_TEMPERATURE_P01",
      "skip_fill_values": false,
      "optional": true
    },
    {
      "column_name": "COMMON_TEMPERATURE_P06",
      "alias": "COMMON_TEMPERATURE_P06",
      "skip_fill_values": false,
      "optional": true
    },
    {
      "column_name": "COMMON_SALINITY",
      "alias": "COMMON_SALINITY",
      "skip_fill_values": true,
      "optional": true
    }
  ]
}
    
```

Figure 5- Beacon KPI monitoring dashboard showing query performed by user

Figure 6 - Beacon KPI monitoring dashboard showing the number of queries and data sets per user

These monolithic Beacon instances can be used by the WorkBench teams, but also by all other VRE users, such as Blue-Cloud Vlabs. For using, potential users have to request a token from MARIS.

3.2. Merged Beacon instances configured for WorkBench 1 and WorkBench 2

Common Metadata - Data Model for merged Beacon instances

As a next step, specifically for the two WorkBenches 1 and 2, two integrated Beacon instances have been initiated. These Beacon instances are merging data set collections from selected monolithic Beacon instances. The challenge here is to deliver harmonised collections, federated from the monolithic instances with different data models. For that purpose, the WB teams have formulated a core metadata – data profile which should be populated by extracting and mapping from the monolithic instances.

Key metadata	Description
source BDI	
unique identifier in the source BDI	SeaDataNet/EMODnet Chemistry Local CDI+EDMO CMEMS CORA/EuroArgo DC_REFERENCE+id WOD Accession number/ database ID
access date to source BDI	YYYY-MM-DD
platform	L06 (types), B76 (models) and C17 (instances)
instrument	L05 (types) and L22 (models)
variable	P01
variable standard name	P07 (if required) - could be derived from P01 or I-ADOPT mappings
units	P06
quality flag	L27 for identification of source flag scheme, and L20 (SeaDataNet) and/or L34 (IODE) for harmonisation
time	YYYY-MM-DD THH:MM:SSZ in 24 hours mode and UTC
geographic position	reference coordinate system WGS84
depth	
organisation (originator, holding centre)	EDMO code
project	EDMERP code
cruise	CSR
date update	

Table 2 - Common Metadata and Data Profile for merged Beacon instances, including target vocabularies

Remark: The header fields in this table provide information to be able to track back the data to the source BDI, where the full data and metadata reside.

Table 3.1 already indicates which monolithic Beacon instances will be combined into the two merged Beacon instances, one for WorkBench 1 (T&S) and one for WorkBench 2 (eutrophication).

Syntactic and semantic harmonisation

For each monolithic Beacon instance, the fields have been determined which correspond to the target fields included in the Common Metadata - Data Profile. Their content is extracted into the merged Beacon instances. This process harmonises not only syntax, but also aims at harmonising content by matching the terms (or URIs when present) used by the source BDIs to the common targeted vocabularies. The

harmonisation focuses on instruments (models or types), platforms (instances or types) , parameters and units, as well as other core metadata elements. For this merging, use is made of the federated queries capability of Beacon, and of the domain- and semantic expertise held at NOC-BODC assisted by the use of the Semantic Analyser software as developed and operated by NOC-BODC. Both the original content and the mapped concepts are included in the merge to help with traceability and transparency.

Figure 7 - Schematic building of Merged Beacon instances by federation and harmonisation

For Beacon it is necessary to learn the required fields, mappings and unit conversions which will be formulated as filters in Beacon for efficient conversion from heterogeneous input to homogeneous output. For the formulation of the mappings, MARIS as Beacon developer and operator relies on the WorkBench teams that are more knowledgeable about the different data collections and their scientific contents. They are supported in this effort by NOC-BODC who is advising on semantic mappings and operating and managing the **Semantic Analyser (SA)**.

The **Semantic Analyser** (<https://semantics.bodc.ac.uk/>) is a software tool to analyse the semantic elements of metadata and data files from a wide range of data resources across multiple domains (atmospheric, marine, terrestrial). The SA is capable of extracting semantic content from metadata and data files encoded in various formats. Upon completion of the analysis, the SA provides a list of terms that have been successfully extracted, along with information about the matched semantic artefacts. Analyses are performed against the Semantic Analyser Knowledge Base which has been populated using vocabularies used by BDIs. This is facilitating the mapping of elements from a number of core metadata profile elements that are supported by SeaDataNet vocabularies such as platforms types (L06) and instances (C17), instruments types (L05) and model (L22). The development of the Semantic Analyser is shared with the EU FAIR-EASE project which serves as a development space for the Blue-Cloud 2026 project. To facilitate the SA mappings, MARIS is providing so-called footprints of the original contents retrieved from the monolithic Beacon instances for the common metadata and data fields. The footprints contain the unique values as derived from each monolithic beacon, which NOC-BODC tries to resolve against the SA Knowledge Base. The returned mappings are then integrated in Beacon to produce homogeneous outputs of queries.

Figure 8 - Architecture of the Semantic Analyser (SA) of NOC-BODC

For both WorkBenches, there is a focus on those parameters that are relevant for the specific WorkBench EOVs, and striving for harmonisation of individual parameters by using their mapping to the SeaDataNet P01 BODC Parameter Usage Vocabulary: <https://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P01/current/> and, in some cases, to the P07 Climate and Forecast Standard Names: https://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P07/current

A new vocabulary (the EXV collection) has been created as a collection of terms used for Essential Variable concepts across the environmental domain at <https://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/EXV/current>. This provides a SKOS collection for all EV concepts to be used in projects to support SKOS mappings.

Interoperability and flexible data search and aggregation functionality can be supported by decomposing the Blue-Cloud variables (parameters) using I-ADOPT. The **I-ADOPT Framework Ontology** is a lightweight ontology primarily designed to facilitate interoperability between existing variable description models (including ontologies, taxonomy, and structured controlled vocabularies). In 2023 the ontology was extended to support the aggregation of variables using a range of user-defined coarser concepts to facilitate dataset discovery and aggregation into products.

Figure 9 - Enabling cross-domain semantic discovery and interoperability at the parameter level

Applying the I-ADOPT Framework means:

1. decompose the variable in atomic components
2. assign a description role for each component
3. annotate each component with concepts from terminologies

See also: <https://i-adopt.github.io/index.html>

The EXV concepts are instances of the I-ADOPT class VariableSet and can therefore be decomposed as described in Figure 3.8, and matched to components of parameters used in the datasets if these parameters have also been expressed using the I-ADOPT decomposition approach (Table 3.3).

EV ID	EV Label	Property	Object of Interest	Matrix
EXV017	Sea-surface temperature	Temperature (unspecified, ITS-90 and IPTS68)	Water body	Not applicable
EXV018	Subsurface temperature	Temperature (unspecified, ITS-90 and IPTS68)	Water body	Not applicable
EXV019	Sea-surface salinity	Practical salinity and Salinity	Water body	Not applicable
EXV020	Subsurface salinity	Practical salinity and Salinity	Water body	Not applicable
EXV023	Sea level	Surface elevation	Water body	Not applicable
EXV028	Oxygen	Concentration	Oxygen	Water body
EXV029	Nutrients	Concentration	Nitrate, nitrite, nitrate+nitrite, phosphate, silicate	Water body

Table 3 - Decomposition of EXVs of relevance for WorkBenches 1 and 2 using I-Adopt

For example, the decomposition of EXV018 - Subsurface temperature - in the EXV vocabulary gives relations with the following S21 and S06 concepts:

- S21: S21S027 water body
- S06: S0600082 Temperature
- S06: S0600160 Temperature (IPTS-68)
- S06: S0600161 Temperature (ITS-90)

Checking the S06 concepts, one can then find relations with P01 terms that have the properties “Temperature” or “Temperature (IPTS-68)” or “Temperature (ITS-90)”. In the case of the first S06 concept (S0600082) this returns 167 P01 concepts if the matrix is not specified (Fig 3.9). The results can be further filtered by including the Object-type of interest (e.g. “water body”).

The NERC Vocabulary Server (NVS)

Service Status

[NVS Home](#) | [Vocabularies](#) | [Thesauri](#) | [Search NVS](#) | [SPARQL](#) | [Other Tools](#) | [About NVS](#)

Concept

Temperature

URI <http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/S06/current/S0600082/>

Within Vocab BODC parameter semantic model parameter entity names

Alternative Labels

Definition The degree of hotness of an object, a measurement matrix, an environment, expressed against a standard scale.

Date 2017-09-18T16:26:

Identifier SDN:S06::S0600082

Note accepted

Has Current Version 1

version 1

Same As QUDT <http://qudt.org/vocab/quantitykind/Temperature> Mapping: 390580

Broader S01:S014 parameter entity Mapping: 1450382

Narrower

P01 BODC Parameter Usage Vocabulary - (167) [-]

P01: CTMP1001 Temperature 10-minute mean of the atmosphere Mapping: 1591289

P01: CATAVT10 Temperature 10-minute mean of the atmosphere by in-situ thermometer Mapping: 1591271

P01: CATAVT02 Temperature 2-minute mean of the atmosphere by in-situ Mapping: 1591281

Alternate Formats

Other formats for this page:

[RDF/XML](#) [Turtle](#) [JSON-LD](#)

Alternate Profiles

Other views of this page:

[Alternate Profiles](#) ?

[NVS html view](#) ?

Figure 10 - NVS page for S06 concept giving P01 relations

Finally, mappings and conversion rules in case of parameters and units are provided by NOC-BODC to MARIS for on-the-fly use in Beacon to produce homogeneous outputs of queries based on relationships established between P06 concepts for unit of measurements in the NVS, and matching unit concepts and unit conversion functionality maintained at <https://www.qudt.org/>.

Deployed merged Beacon instances

Beta versions of the two merged Beacon instances, one for each WorkBench 1 and 2, have been deployed and are made available at the MARIS server. These are being finalised, using the latest semantic mappings, and updating the T&S data sets from SeaDataNet. Once validated and approved, these will also be

deployed at the Blue-Cloud VRE, together with Jupyter notebooks on top of the APIs for easy operation. The following table gives the composition and URLs of the two merged Beacon instances.

Beacon instance, merging BDI data collections	Merged Beacon instance	WorkBench
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● CORA Profile data, retrieved from Copernicus Marine Service: INSITU_GLO_PHY_TS_DISCRETE_MY_013_001 ● CORA Timeseries, retrieved from Copernicus Marine Service: INSITU_GLO_PHY_TS_DISCRETE_MY_013_001 ● Euro-Argo data, retrieved from S3 bucket ● World Ocean Database (WOD) actual depths, retrieved from ncei.noaa.gov ● SeaDataNet T&S data collection, retrieved from SeaDataNet CDI service³ 	beacon-wb1-ts.maris.nl	WorkBench 1
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EMODnet Chemistry North East Atlantic Collection (subset of the complete collection) retrieved from EMODnet Chemistry WebODV (Eutrophication_Atlantic_profiles_2023_unrestricted.odv) ● World Ocean Database (WOD) actual depths, retrieved from ncei.noaa.gov ● BGC data, retrieved from Copernicus Marine Service: 	beacon-wb2-eutrophication.maris.nl	WorkBench 2

³Initially, the SeaDataNet CDI data collection concerned the SeaDataCloud T&S data product complemented with SeaDataNet CDI data sets from 2019. This is being replaced by a full T&S data collection from SeaDataNet CDI service, resulting in an updated merged Beacon instance

Beacon instance, merging BDI data collections	Merged Beacon instance	WorkBench
INSITU_GLO_BGC_DISCRETE_MY_013_046		

Table 4 - Overview of deployed merged Beacon instances

The WorkBench teams will use the two merged Beacon instances to prepare subsets and export these in a homogeneous way (concerning parameters, units, and core metadata) for loading into analytical applications at the Blue-Cloud VRE for further processing steps, such as identifying and removing duplicate data sets, validating and harmonising quality flags, and finally, generation of the highly qualified, validated, and harmonised data set collections for selected Essential Ocean Variables (EOVs).

One of these analytical applications is the **webODV online service**. webODV has been developed and is maintained by AWI and is an online version of the very popular ODV software. Previously, webODV was only available as a ‘read-only’ service to browse and extract data sets from imported ODV data collections and to make plots. As part of the Blue-Cloud 2026 project, AWI has developed a new version of webODV which is now a ‘read and write’ version which features many functionalities for analyses, plots, annotations, and exports.

As a standard, Beacon gives its output in NetCDF, but for webODV, the ASCII ODV data format is required. Therefore, MARIS and AWI have developed an export option with an alternative output driver which facilitates Beacon to generate ASCII ODV output files which then can be loaded into WebODV. To be able to produce an ODV, Beacon has to split its single harmonised response format into various categories such as, profiles, time series and trajectories. This splitting is required as Beacon harmonises everything to a single output format (eg. profiles, time series and trajectories are all stored/represented in the same manner) while ODV requires them to be split into separate categories. To perform this splitting, AWI has created a script that recognizes the differences between profiles, time series and trajectories. This script splits the ODV file that Beacon creates into separate ODV files. This script is available at: https://github.com/smieruch/beacon_odv_exporter. While MARIS has created a Beacon ODV output driver that can generate the input for AWI’s script that splits these ODV files which Beacon repackages as a single ZIP file. This has been tested by the WorkBench teams.

4. Conclusions and follow-up

It can be concluded that very good progress has been made so far with configuring and deploying Beacon data lakes for multiple data collections from BDIs, which are relevant as input for WorkBenches 1 and 2. A total of 8 monolithic Beacon instances have been deployed at a MARIS server and, after testing also at the Blue-Cloud VRE.

Furthermore, two beta instances of merged Beacon data lakes have been deployed, one for WorkBench 1 and one for WorkBench 2. These are for now only at a MARIS server, where these are being tested by WB team members and being finalised. For the T&S merged Beacon there is work ongoing for including the full T&S data collection from the SeaDataNet CDI service, while initially this was different. Finalisation of the merged instances also requires making further mappings by NOC-BODC of free text lists of terms extracted from the BDI, assisted by the Semantic Analyser software system, and completing the implementation of the I-ADOPT approach for variable mapping. These mappings will then be integrated into Beacon by MARIS for on-the-fly harmonisation of the Beacon outputs.

In addition, an export routine has been developed by MARIS and AWI to generate ASCII ODV output from the merged Beacon instances which can be loaded into one of the analytical applications, namely webODV, that the WB Teams will use for further processing of the Beacon output data sets.

There is a WP3 workshop planned 26-28 March 2025 at IFREMER in Brest - France where the WB Teams will discuss the next steps for their analytical activities and the interaction between different tools and services in the planned analytical pipelines. MARIS, AWI and NOC-BODC will participate in this Workshop to give support for use of the merged Beacon instances. It is planned that the two merged Beacon instances will be fully ready and also made available at the Blue-Cloud VRE before that Workshop.

As a follow-up, a few more activities are foreseen concerning the Beacon data lakes:

- A number of the BDI data collections are dynamic and regularly maintained with new and/or updated data entries. Therefore, MARIS will work on establishing regular maintenance in a structural way of relevant monolithic Beacon instances, which then also should update the merged Beacon instance through the federation of the monolithic instances.
- The two merged Beacon instances will become part of the analytical pipelines of the WB Teams. For an efficient practice it will be essential for WB Teams to have access to information about which data sets they already had loaded from Beacon into other analytical components for further processing and which might be new or updated data sets. With this information, the WB Teams can then organise analytical runs without duplicating efforts. For this purpose, MARIS will develop a dashboard for WB Teams that will keep track of output batches and their status.

Next to the activities directly relevant to the WB Teams, MARIS also plans to work with CINECA on a Beacon instance for the full collection of open SeaDataNet CDI data sets, which should be in sync with the current SeaDataNet CDI service. The latter service includes an open data cache at CINECA, which is part of the shopping mechanism of the SeaDataNet CDI service. The CDI service works with predefined data sets, while using Beacon, the functionality of the SeaDataNet CDI service can be expanded with sub-setting on the data sets, which are included and maintained in the central data cache. This concerns data files for circa 3 million CDI entries which is increasing regularly as part of regular submissions by SeaDataNet data centres. An important element of the synchronised SeaDataNet Beacon instance will be that it will merge both the metadata from the CDI catalogue and the elements from the actual data sets. This will create a powerful service which will enrich the SeaDataNet CDI service for many users and multiple uses. This Beacon instance will be deployed at the CINECA infrastructure in sync and next to the SeaDataNet CDI data cache. These activities will start in April 2025.